

EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES USING IOT-DRIVEN IN HEALTHCARE : SURVEY, CHALLENGES AND FUTURE

Manthan Jitendra Joshi

Assistant professor, SLRTCE, Thane.

ABSTRACT

By the rise in the population factor of the country like India the number of diseases also increases since in the rise of the population. The health care system in our country is not that efficient that it can treat the people on time. As we have seen during the pandemic it was not that easy for doctor to treat all the people at a time due to shortage of doctors over the people which there was loss of life. The paper will speak about the different technology like IOT in the field of medicine and healthcare device such as ECG, temperature, glucose, asthma etc. With the help of this technology where the doctor can reach the maximum people through network with the use of wearable device at home with the help of IoT. We will also see how the WBAN system works. We will also see the concept of telemedicine and benefits in the health-care industry. so basically this paper will brief you about the concept, working of WBAN in the healthcare industry system. Since lot of work is carried out but still there is much work to be carried out in the field of IoT in healthcare. In this report gives exhaustive study on the different technology used in the medicine and health-care sector with the different IoT sensor can be used at remote or rural as well as in hospital and at home to check the different parameter for live measurement. The report also talks on the IIOT in the robotic surgery using the AI and ML technology for the surgery purpose and even the robot can use in the room to monitor the patient if doctor and nurse are not available.

Keywords: IoT, WBAN, ROBOTIC, ECG, GLUCOSE

Cite this Article: Manthan Jitendra Joshi. Emerging Technologies using IOT-Driven in Healthcare : Survey, Challenges and Future. *International Journal of Computer Engineering and Technology (IJCET)*, 15(3), 2024, pp. 21-36.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJCET/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_3/IJCET_15_03_004.pdf

1. INTRODUCTION

In the today's modern life people are very careless of their health because of their living style, working schedule and even their eating styles. so this paper will basically talk about the IoT in health-care sector and their methods through the wireless technology and the diagnosis method for the remote health diagnosis system. E-health body area network which is also called as the wireless body area network (WBANs) which is been now in the great demand and have gain lot of research with the help of IoT technology and has shown the incredible assistances for the people living in the rural area or for the remote location where its difficult to reach for continuous care. [2] (Ashwini Gutte and et al. (2018)) This helps us to continuous look after the people with real-time care. With the advancement in electronic technology the sensor has become compact with the integrated circuit and wireless communication using IoT has help us to get new generation of WSN (wireless sensor network). E-health body area network (E- BAN) can also be called as the WBAN which can be used as the the portable devices where patient can wear on the hand or can easily put the system on the body which will be discussed in the further part for the easy monitoring of different data. Body area network is a network basically used to detect and monitor the working system of human body. The purpose of this network is to provide the real time data that is been send by the wearable device outside the wireless local area network or the internet. In some of the cases the data can be transmitted directly to each other using different technology.

There are different type of measuring device available in market in the digital as well as analog form in hospital as well as at home such as the ECG monitoring of patient heart, measuring the blood pressure of the body in both analog and digital form is available in market, blood sugar monitoring for the sugar patient, temperature sensor such as digital and analog thermometer at each ones home which we get in easily at everyone home, this are some of the common health measuring meters etc. that are currently available in the market. Due to the increase in the work, overtime of work pressure The number of chronic diseases have been collectively gained within the recent times where now-days seen small children have become affected with chronic disease. All over the world the population is getting older as par the statis between the year 2017 to 2050 person with the age 60 years and above is expected to increase more than the double i.e. in the year 1980 there were 382 million older people all over the world whereas in coming years till 2050 it is expected to be 2.1 billion older people worldwide. [2]Ashwini Gutte and et al.(2018), Different diseases are increasing all over the world as we have seen the covid-19 diseases which have almost stop the world for year and half and still it has been not gone out of one is individual so it is challenging that at any time any diseases or virus can harm individual so the health-care for day-to-day is necessary. Since the different diseases are increasing or even with the regular diseases one need to regularly go to doctor for the routine check-up which not only increases the expenditure but also need time for the regular check-up from the daily schedule. There also increase in the expenditure of hospitals as well as medical clinic if person need to go daily for check-up. Next challenge is at many people in the rural areas or remote area the internet or computer is not their doctor needs to keep the record of patient in files or in form of paper. Which becomes very difficult to ones if one- or two-year-old record required so this is also one of the challenges that is required to overcome at remote area

2. OBJECTIVE

- To Provide better treatment to the people using the latest technology in the healthcare domain.

- To Collect the real time data analysis & physical constraint of a patient time to time.
- To give accessibility of data to doctor as well as patient, when necessary, at any place, any time on server.
- To Provide better treatment before it becomes serious disease.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

[1] This paper on the whole talks concerning the survey or a evaluate of the on-going analysis in WBANs in terms of system design, address distribution, routing, channel modeling, PHY layer, MAC layer, security and applications is provided. Associate evaluation of WBANs with relevance Wireless sensing detail community technology and alternative wireless technologies is given. WBANs can give continuous observance of patients in medical programs, able to early detection of ordinary conditions leading to most important enhancements inside the first- class of lifestyles. Significantly, even fundamental very crucial symptoms observance (e.G., coronary heart charge) will adjust sufferers to have interaction in conventional sports as antagonistic being domestic positive or near specialised medical services. In precis, the procedural analysis on this precious generation has essential importance in higher usage of available assets that could no doubt have an impact on our destiny properly-being. We generally tend to accept as true with this analysis to be a deliver of proposal closer to destiny traits in WBANs. In this paper it basically talks approximately the generation used is IEEE

802.15.6 that's wi-fi generation used Wearable Health Monitoring, Patient Monitoring, Tele-remedy Systems, Real Time Streaming which fits on Wireless Body Area Networks, Wireless Sensor Networks. The important research hole is that of virtual nurse. Virtual nurse is the idea that there is no need of medical doctor for the fundamental or such treatment where if health practitioner need is not required. Virtual nurse is basically the idea of drugs that the software program will automatically analysis and prescribe the medication on its own like an synthetic intelligence health practitioner or nurse. Depending on the measured price of scientific sensor the virtual nurse will mechanically give the prescribed remedy which may be valid to take from the pharmacy. Which can right away offer the treatment till the medical doctor isn't always available. With the help of this if the health practitioner isn't available for a while so with this a alleviation to the affected person can be given.

[3] This paper discusses the health system supported concept of the Internet of Things and its controller-based projected implementation. Following the basic MQTT protocol of the IoT it is a remote health monitoring application. It helps to identify patients with more chronic diseases. This approach helps in maintaining the health of the elderly who cannot go to the hospital regularly. After basic health check square measure also played simple. The patient history is stored on the server and then the follow-up is sent. Because it uses info technology for evaluation human errors it gives better performance. The technology used in this paper uses IoT technology. IoT consists of many devices, primarily used for patients that range from sensors and monitoring devices such as glucose, blood pressure, heart rate & activity monitoring to connect to the internet, transforming physical world information into digital world. The protocol used is the MQTT protocol for sending and receiving data in the cloud. The main research gap is that of the virtual nurse. Virtual Nurse is the concept of not having to have a doctor for basic or similar treatments where if not having to have a doctor. The Virtual Nurse is basically a medical concept that software will analyze and prescribe medications for someone like an artificial intelligence doctor or nurse. Based on the measured value in the medical sensor, the virtual nurse will automatically dispense a prescription that may be worth picking up from the pharmacy. which can be cured immediately unless a doctor is present. With the help of this, if the doctor is not available for a while, this can make the patient feel better.

[6] Ageing populations and consequently the growth in persistent diseases anywhere the arena demand reasonably-priced tending answers for maintaining properly-being of individuals. One method that has drawn essential evaluation interest may be a give attention to remote fitness monitoring systems supported internet of Things (IoT) era. This concept will facilitate decrease stress on sanatorium structures and tending providers, cut back tending prices, and improve homecare mainly for sufferers with continual diseases and therefore the elderly. This paper explores the employment of IoT-based totally programs in scientific subject companion degreed proposes an IoT layer layout (IoTTA) closer to accomplice degree technique for transforming tool statistics into time scientific comments. This approach considers a range of elements inclusive of sensing, sending, processing, storing, and mining and learning. Mistreatment this technique can facilitate to broaden useful and powerful answers for following systems improvement in IoT healthcare applications. The consequences of the evaluation observed that the boom of IoT packages for tending is in areas of self-care, statistics mining, and gadget gaining knowledge of. The generation used inside the paper is definitely based totally within the IoT that how the information is been processed as noted in the above paragraph. It also talks approximately the telecare the right way to preserve their fitness from domestic the usage of telecare or tele- remedy. Self-care is likewise one issue that is been mentioned by using the usage of the IoT tool or sensor. As seen within the research hole the garage and keeping of massive records that is huge facts remains an problem. As in the area of drugs the excessive MB, GB of pictures inside the remedy of ECG, CANCER AND OTHER DISEASES continues to be an trouble to store the records at the cloud. With the aid of storing the big records the documents get effortlessly corrupted or adjustments of threatening the information is easy. So, the difficulty needs to be solved as rapid as viable. Even if the records has been saved however the records has been no longer analyzed then the storing of information is wastage so the technology of ML and AI is ought to investigate the statistics after storing to get the right result.

[14] This paper deals with the rising advances in internet of Things (IoT) and big records analytics for medicinal drug and health care technologies thinking of the reducing age evaluation work allotted globally. IoT and huge expertise analytics are expected to revolutionize numerous fields together with remedy and health care technologies as all of us realize it today. The contents on rising traits in IoT and massive understanding analytics for the subsequent developments are highlighted with examples Telemedicine: Telemedicine complements the technological increase surprisingly in numerous regions together with IP, medication, materials technology, telecommunications, artificial intelligence, digital presence, and robotics. Telemedicine system is improving the fitness care performance with the aid of fee reduction, AI. The foremost intention of this bankruptcy is to discover the severa roles of IoT, AI and huge figures in fitness care generation. This section principally specializes in the four principal programs: remote affected person watching, clinical information technology, scientific records evaluation, and accurate diagnosing with correct decision-making era. Here telerobotic surgical operation and also the importance of IoRT. Wearable Devices and IoT: A wave of wearable devices concentrated on the medical area of expertise and health care programs way on the some distance facet chase your steps daily has emerged. These devices are degree capable of collection careful data concerning our fitness, whereas moreover serving as a smartwatch or easy attachment blended with our mobile telephones. The information

amassed and analyzed in regular protocols by way of gadget intelligence looking for doable predictions of health-related troubles. At the a ways facet those prosthetic technologies combined with the advanced materials, design, computing and synthetic intelligence has created big development and now chip-based or auxiliary motors or synthetic intelligence devices based totally in most cases useful structures are measure possible. Overall, IoT and massive facts analytics are most important technology that can redecorate the biomedical and health care area and create human existence more healthy. Large records applies to health care and clinical drugs. The core of massive information analytics relies on volume of data generated, alternate of facts hooked up i.E., extraordinary categories along side, facts advent velocity, unpredictability, i.E., the day loophole, incomplete lowliness in some information. Thinking about those 5 variables and many further factors, case basis, and massive statistics analytics may be quite complicated. For biomedical and fitness care, huge records analytics can technique complicated and massive datasets. The assets of maximum of the drugs and fitness care information are measured normally through medical statistics, scientific photo and records uploaded from varied sensors in centralized structures from, operations, pharmaceutical information etc. Robotic generation, machine studying, AI, and swarm technologies can supply the longer-time period improvement of the IoT packages. Today, the most rising internet of Robotic Things (IoRT) brings new convergence troubles like programmability and consequently the communication between severa cellular/robotic matters for higher coordination, change of records, safety, configuration, and protection. Robotic arms are employed to keep out far off surgical ranges with smart accuracy. Depicts the various applications of telemedicine for health monitoring. The studies gap from this paper is that still there is not as boost in the subject of robotics in medicine. The automation technique for robotic surgery by using the way of ML and AI is still lagging. There is still some trouble with the operation purpose with the robot arm which can not characteristic all the require matters.

4. ARCHITECTURE

1. IOT IN HEALTH-CARE SYSTEM

Fig 4.1 iot in health care[1]Samaneh Movassaghi et al.(2014)

2.3 TIER ARCHITECTURE

fig 4.2 : Architecture[5]Krishnan, D. S. R., et al. (2018).

5. IOT HEALTHCARE SENSOR

A. ECG

Nowadays there are specific healthcare devices. Wireless ECG monitors are there that may accumulate bio alerts from this ECG gadgets, ECG sensors; the amassed information may be despatched to the cloud, clinical staffs can examine the fitness-related statistics in real time. In truth, you can have a few programs and technology like AI that can autonomously analyze the information which are coming in and may ship signals. So, one instance of a wi-fi IOT enabled ECG sensor is QardioCore. QardioCore is a tool for ECG monitoring, it's miles a wi-fi device. QARDIOCORE is the arena first ECG reveal tool. Which was essentially made for the those who had the records of coronary heart attack, excessive blood pressure, excessive ldl cholesterol, and extra weight so as to check their ordinary screen their fitness situation Some of the functions of QARDIOCORE

- Track your complete heart fitness in your cellphone
- Get a clinically authenticated electrocardiograph trace for deeper heart health understandings
- Share information together with your doctor robotically
- Continuous recording approach

Fig 5.1: QARDIOCORE ECG SENSOR

B. GLUCOSE

For the sugar monitoring particularly for diabetes patients; patients with the diabetes need to check their sugar level quite often or frequently. Mostly, the patient who have high degree or level of diabetes; since they are required to check the blood sugar frequently, but quite often. So, if you have an device which is IOT based automatically enabled to which the patients can be fitted, which basically send the data automatically of the different patient that can be made available to whoever the data require for the analysis such as such as doctors who are treating the diabetes patient. For example for sugar monitoring device is the Dexcom.

DEXCOM G6 CGM is a system that will help you to see your sugar level and where its heading without tickling on the fingerstick. This system will helps to achieve your sugar level of different such as Type 1 or Type 2 diabetes [19].

SOME OF THE FEATURES OF DEXCOM

1. Features of this device is that it will Help the person to keep the sugar level in Control.
2. Zero Fingerstick--The Dexcom G6 is FDA- permitted to make diabetes treatment decisions without assenting fingerstick.
3. Customizable Alerts & Alarms—this device will give you the alert and alarms if the range goes lower or higher to patients as well as to the doctor on the daily basis.
4. Share Your Glucose Data- This has also as an feature to Share data on app as shown in the fig with up to 10 people

Fig 5.2: DEXON glucose sensor

C. OXYGEN

This is very important for oxygen saturation intensive care, especially for people affected by asthma, oxygen saturation can be monitored with the benefit of IOT device such as pulse oximeter. Thus, a pulse oximeter can help to measure oxygen saturation so that this pulse oximeter can be connected to bluetooth and other communication solutions to continuously transmit data about the monitored oxygen saturation level of that patient or person.

D. BLOOD PRESSURE

We have IIoT based blood pressure monitoring system. IIoT devices can be used to measure a patient's blood pressure and compare it with other blood pressures in real time. Doctors can monitor a patient's blood pressure in real time; Blood pressure can receive alerts when it processes a certain threshold such as the heigher level or lower level of prerssure and allows doctors to prescribe medications to patients based on blood pressure data received by the system monitoring. One such example of a blood pressure monitoring system is the QARDIOARM

QARDIOARM is the smart blood pressure monitoring. It displays your results on a color-coded WHO chart. The color display is shown below. This type of reading you will get to see on the screen of the qardio app.

Fig 5.3: QARDIOARM app screen

Some of the feature of QARDIOARM

- Usual reminders meant for repetitive measurements, share them with your doctor.
- Triple measurement average for the most accurate readings.
- Combined with Apple Health and S Health for calm administration.
- Irregular Heart Beat Detection
- Result Interpretation
- Easy Data Sharing
- Geo Tracking

Fig 5.4: QARDIOARM blood pressure sensor

E. TEMPERATURE

Body temperature monitors, there are multiple wearable sensors for continuous monitoring of human body temperature. This is sometimes very necessary for patients who suffer from some diseases to make the continuous monitoring of body temperature is mandatory. There are

different Type of body temperature sensors in the market one such body temperature sensor is from Kinsa. So, they take their smart thermometer which is an IOT installed body temperature 24-hour care device. which can be used in home as well as in hospital.[18]

Separate profile: Monitor fever and symptoms for entire family.

- Revised guidance: Get real-time age and disease-based approvals to experience faster improvement.
- Best protection: Keep a log of your family health and part on timeline with doctor.
- Medication information Track and recall medication prescriptions Set up.
- COVID-19 Support: Symptoms and Diagnosis Support .
- Local Risk: Know the increasingly nearby diseases so you can take appropriate actions to stay healthy

Fig 5.5: Kinsa body temperature

F. CONTACT LENSE

- There are also IoT based contact lenses in the market. There are various IoT-based contact lenses that also offer Wi-Fi connectivity with a smartphone to monitor the patient's condition, eye condition, and sugar levels, etc.
- Tear glucose level detection and diabetes diagnosis quickly by IoT It can be a mirror of possibility.
- Researchers are working to provide a solution for presbyopia (a disease in which the retina is weak) with sensor-based contact lenses.
- In the near future, medications may be administered to the eye, preferably instead of eye drops.
- Like other applications – Eyeball's continuous monitoring will add another feature.

Fig 5.6: contact lens

G. ASTHAMA

IOT built bronchial asthma treatment resolutions at the moment are within the marketplace. Smart Inhaler inhalers are a very important requirement of bronchial asthma patients. So, Smart Inhalers had been synthetic. So, ADAMM[17] is an smart asthma monitoring device that has been evolved. So, this tool can keep music of the body temperature, coughing fee, coronary heart price and so forth. Which can be frequently preliminary signs and symptoms of an bronchial

asthma bronchial asthma attack.

Fig 4.6: ADAMM asthma sensor

- **Wearable Device**

ADAMM is a cushty, patch-kind wearable that can be worn at the aspect, the front or back of the top torso in any orientation. It's so discreet, no one might even know it's beneath your clothing. Work, socialize, exercise or sleep with it, even as you're carrying your device it will constantly display your signs and symptoms. Recharge it each 14 – 18 hours.

- **Smartphone App**

ADAMM will display and report your signs, tracking cough; respiration styles; heart rate; skin temperature and hobby degree. More than that you could track your medicines, magazine your notes, and set notifications and reminders thru the app. This facts is uploaded for your cellphone as and while you synch it and may be reviewed for your portal.

- Web Portal

You can get admission to your secure private net portal to view and manipulate your statistics and you have the selection and potential to proportion this records with your healthcare company. Data is accumulated and saved in compliance with the POPI Act.

6. HEALTH CARE USING ROBOTICA AND AI

1. ROBOTIC SURGERY

The healthcare industry is becoming more complex by the day, and over time, researchers are connecting devices via the Internet. Current day-to-day use of IIOT for surgery to surgery, in effect, doctors use IoT-enabled robotic devices. This small robotic device can perform surgery inside the patient's body Doctor used to perform the operation by hands which is not much accurate operation has become more accurate and successful. That is the people recovery is much faster due to robotic surgery.[13] Alina Saduova, et al. (2021),“

Fig 5.1 robotic surgery

Some of the critical points of robotic surgical operation

- It makes it possible to perform the operation from the distant location, that may save many lives each inside the health facility and conflict area.
- Performing surgical operation operation by way of doctor for a protracted hour can be a problem from time to time. The use of a robotic device can remedy this hassle. Protection threat may be high as gadgets are related to the internet.

Uses of robot surgical operation

- Smart medical pills
- Surgical robotics
- Prosthetics the usage of Surgical robots
- Motor co-ordination analysis and remedy through robots
- Robot assisted intellectual and social remedy
- Robotized affected person monitoring structures

2. AI In Robotic

AI is used to increase the potential of a laptop- enabled robotic structure to talk information and bring desirable results. The AI machine examines a selection support approach for important care and detects the extent of recognition by means of the health professionals. AI improves the affected person communication and will increase the system ability to process and shop big

quantities of records in a clever way. AI plays a main role in health care that could accumulate the numerous technologies enabling machines to sense, act, and research, for you to carry out administrative and scientific features. The AI is widely targeted in lots of regions like control machine (MIS), facts flow, rule-based structures, information-mining, deep neural networks, machine learning, case-based reasoning, facts visualization, and tele-robot, respectively. AI is used for severa packages which includes photo popularity and interpretation, diagnostic help, developing reminders and signals, remedy making plans, and many others. AI offers fast and correct diagnostics to reduce human mistakes, price discount, digital presence, and telemedicine.[13] Alina Saduova, et al. (2021) ,“

3. Internet of robot Things

Robotic generation, independent capabilities, and IoT collectively presents an amazing bring about phrases of the Internet of Robotic Things (IoRT). IoRT is the maximum difficult framework in which clever devices can obtain sensor records from sufferers and technique to a cloud server in a clever manner in terms of right choice-making unit. It takes faster results, right visualization, and records manipulation, information acquisition, analytics, and verbal exchange. IoRT is used to experience, statistics collection, movement, manipulation, mobility, and intelligence that improves the IoT services. ML combined robot generation offers higher smart with IoT in which numerous robots can get interconnected. The primary processor-controlled robots via secure Wi-Fi networks. AI based totally IoT robot generation to be associated with IoT programs for offering optimized results over packages. The aggregate of the internet and automaton is giving new answers to a exclusive enterprise. We tend to talk regarding robots which could assist the nurse in the medical institution, that is a rare development of IoT and health region. Robots in every affected person’s room will construct the remedy extra practical. At a similar time, it facilitates nurses in numerous methods that like providing medicinal drug and instrumentation or giving an alert for the fast and fixed task and so more This answer not hardly ever helps nurses but can also communicate with the patient, which components them a number of consolation. Nurses will set up their personal commands constant with their personal agenda. Can smooth the gap for logo spanking new patients if any affected person discharged. Reduces the mental feature load of nurses, that brings a variety of potentials. This utility designed in a very manner that it must be non- threatening and doable with the aid of Internet and cellular apps.

Fig 5.2: different robotic surgery instruments

7. TELEMEDICINE AND CLOUD SERVICE

One more advancement in the field of WBAN is the tele-medicine that is we can assets independent of their geographical area i.e., we can connect with the people around the world can help with the medicines or with the new technology in the field of the medicine. Even we can help the doctors practicing and the medical students with the medicinal knowledge. Even doctors at rural area can connect with the doctors at the urban area to consult with the specialist of medicine and surgery. Even today due to this doctor can assist the other doctor for the surgery purpose with this tele-medicine and IoT. We can even collaborate with the multidisciplinary. at the today times we can get the doctor facility 24x7 at just some payment. There are many apps on which we get the facility.

Generally used protocols with IoT based systems are CoAP, MQTT and HTTP. HTTP and MQTT are selected for sensor-based totally packages and in line with the utility's requirement. Here we've got used the ThingSpeak as the cloud platform. ThingSpeak is an open-supply Internet of Things (IoT) server and API to store and save records from matters the usage of the HTTP protocol over the Internet or through a Local Area Network.[5] By the use of ThingSpeak website, we will monitor our facts and manage our machine over the Internet, the use of the Channels and webpages provided by means of ThingSpeak. ThingSpeak 'Collects' the facts from the sensors, 'Analyze and Visualize' the records and 'Acts' with the aid of triggering a reaction [4]. Here the protocol that ThingSpeak uses is the http protocol.

Fig 7.1: ThingSpeak -Thinghttp

The fig above shows the ThingHTTP. We power the use of ThingHTTP software of the server to spark off the IFTTT applet for saved data- statistics get admission to to Google sheets and ship electronic mail/SMS. ThingHTTP allows conversation among devices, web sites, and net offerings at the same time as now not having to implement the protocol on the tool stage. By the use of this ThingHTTP we are able to easily document the information in the form of the excel sheet and may be used because the in addition reference even the use of this, we are able to get hold of the updates on mail and cell.

id	created_at	updated_at	value	device_id
1	2019-05-20 12:00:00	2019-05-20 12:00:00	0.00	111
2	2019-05-20 12:00:00	2019-05-20 12:00:00	0.00	111
3	2019-05-20 12:00:00	2019-05-20 12:00:00	0.00	111
4	2019-05-20 12:00:00	2019-05-20 12:00:00	0.00	111
5	2019-05-20 12:00:00	2019-05-20 12:00:00	0.00	111
6	2019-05-20 12:00:00	2019-05-20 12:00:00	0.00	111
7	2019-05-20 12:00:00	2019-05-20 12:00:00	0.00	111
8	2019-05-20 12:00:00	2019-05-20 12:00:00	0.00	111
9	2019-05-20 12:00:00	2019-05-20 12:00:00	0.00	111
10	2019-05-20 12:00:00	2019-05-20 12:00:00	0.00	111
11	2019-05-20 12:00:00	2019-05-20 12:00:00	0.00	111
12	2019-05-20 12:00:00	2019-05-20 12:00:00	0.00	111
13	2019-05-20 12:00:00	2019-05-20 12:00:00	0.00	111
14	2019-05-20 12:00:00	2019-05-20 12:00:00	0.00	111
15	2019-05-20 12:00:00	2019-05-20 12:00:00	0.00	111

Fig 7.2: ThingSpeak database on excel

8. BENEFITS

With IIoT, one will reveal the affected person’s fitness situation remotely. So, far flung care is possible. Remote actual time continuous commentary of affected person’s health condition 24x7 is possible. Hospital personnel will be expecting the appearance of a affected person of their emergency units; it's also practicable to own hygiene commentary system which would possibly sight the cleanliness of the medical institution and therefore the building. Medical personnel will offer satisfactory scientific offerings with tiny price range exploitation IIoT. So, these are some of the diverse edges that IIoT implementation in care will provide.

9. CHALENEGES

IoT or IIoT tending as definitely distinct challenges; challenges with relevance restricted computational functionality, no longer having the capability to carry out highly-priced operations, demanding situations with relevance having terribly less device reminiscence, electricity dilemma and conjointly taking care of the first-rate of these completely distinct gadgets due to the sufferers themselves square measure cellular. So, consequently this tool themselves rectangular measure wearable gadgets, the sensors themselves also are mobile. So, looked after pleasant of those completely distinctive devices from a technical point of read could be a project; every from a communication and algorithmic reason of read and measure totally different demanding situations.

10. CONCLUSION

The use of wire-less technology in Medical industry is on high demand. This type of application can have an huge impact and helps in contributing in making healthy lives of patients. IoT and Wireless technology are now almost being install in a variety of situations including those in medical cases. By using the IoT medical sensor will help the doctor as well as person for the real time monitoring of health. There must Sensor developed to overcome the battery problem and make device compact. Robotics and AI will play a very important role in the industry 4.0.

REFERENCE

- [1] Samaneh Movassaghi et al.(2014) , Wireless Body Area Networks: A Survey, iee communications surveys & tutorials.
- [2] Ashwini Gutte and et al.(2018), iot based health monitoring system using raspberry pi, fourth international conference on computing communication control and automation (iccubea).
- [3] Muhammad Sheraz et al.(2018), Wireless Body Area Network Security and Privacy Issue in E-Healthcare, International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications, Vol. 9, No. 4.
- [4] Dr. T. Jagannadha Swamy, eSmart: An IoT based Intelligent Health Monitoring and Management System for Mankind, 9th International Conference on Computer Communication and Informatics (ICCCI -2019), Jan. 23 – 25, 2019, Coimbatore, INDIA,2019.
- [5] Krishnan, D. S. R., et al. (2018). An IoT based Patient Health Monitoring System. Proceedings International Conference on Advances in Computing and Communication Engineering, ICACCE 2018, 1–7.
- [6] HoaHong Nguyen, et al. (2017) “A Review on IoTHealthcare Monitoring Applications and a Vision for Transforming Sensor Data into Real- time Clinical Feedback”, in Proc. Of 21st International Conf. on Computer Supported Cooperative Work in Design, IEEE,.
- [7] Internet of Things in Healthcare: applications, benefits, and challenges”, IoT, Health & Fitness, peerbits.
- [8] FadiAl-Turjman,et.al (2018) “Context-Sensitive Access in Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) Healthcare Applications”, IEEE Transactions of Information Informatics,
- [9] Shang F et al.(2013), “Validation of the iHealthBP5 wireless upper arm blood pressure monitor for self-measurement according to the European Society of Hypertension International Protocol revision 2010”, Blood Press Monitor , doi: 10.1097/MBP.0b013e3283638f04, 2013.
- [10] <https://www.getqardio.com/qardiocore-wearable-ecg-ekg-monitor-iphone/>
- [11] ShareemThahir, “6 Applications of IoTin the Healthcare Industry”, CABOT, 2016.
- [12] Ankit R. Patel, et al.(2017),” Vitality of Robotics in Healthcare Industry:An Internet of Things (IoT) Perspective”, Springer International Publishing , DOI 10.1007/978-3-319-49736-5_5
- [13] Alina Saduova, et al. (2021) ,“Self-Adaptive IoT-based Approach for Improving the Decision Making of Active Surgical Robots in Hospitals”, 3rd IEEE Eurasia Conference on Biomedical Engineering, Healthcare and Sustainability, ISBN: 978-1-7281-9304-5.
- [14] Amit Banerjee et al.,” Emerging trends in IoT and big data analytics for biomedical and health care technologies”, Handbook of Data Science Approaches for Biomedical Engineering. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-818318-2.00005>
- [15] Generate | Health ID (ndhm.gov.in)—DIGITAL HEALTH CARD BY GOV OF INDIA

- [16] IoT in Healthcare: 20 Examples That'll Make You Feel Better
- [17] [www.adamm.co.za/-ATHASMA TREATMENT](http://www.adamm.co.za/-ATHASMA_TREATMENT)
- [18] Smart Thermometers with Personalized Guidance | Kinsa Health – BODY TEMPERATURE TREATMENT
- [19] Dexcom G6 Continuous Glucose Monitoring (CGM) System | Zero Fingersticks– GLUCOSE MONITORING

Citation: Manthan Jitendra Joshi. Emerging Technologies using IOT-Driven in Healthcare : Survey, Challenges and Future. International Journal of Computer Engineering and Technology (IJCET), 15(3), 2024, pp. 21-36.

Article Link:

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJCET/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_3/IJCET_15_03_004.pdf

Abstract Link:

https://iaeme.com/Home/article_id/IJCET_15_03_004

Copyright: © 2024 Authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

This work is licensed under a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)**.

editor@iaeme.com